

Phytochemical and pharmacological studies on the seeds of *Centratherum anthelminticum*[†]

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Abstract : One new and two known glycosides were isolated from the seeds of *Centratherum anthelminticum*. The new pentacyclic triterpenoid saponin was shown to contain caulophyllogenin and seven sugar residues forming three glycosyl chains. The structural analysis of its acetylated derivative was determined using a combination of homo-(1D ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and ¹³C NMR-DEPT) and heteronuclear 2D NMR techniques (¹H-¹H-COSY, ¹H-¹H-TOCSY, HMQC and HMBC), ESIMS and chemical methods. The structure of the saponin was established as 3-*O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-[α-L-arabinopyranosyl-(1→5)]-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-28-*O*-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→3)-β-D-glucopyranosyl]-16α,23-acetoxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid. The other compounds β-sitosterol-3-*O*-glucopyranoside and 3-*O*-[β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl]-hederagenin were also isolated from the methanol extract of seeds. Different extracts and compounds were also tested for antifilarial, antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities. Methanolic and aqueous extracts of seeds exhibited some pronounced pharmacological activities under study.

Keywords : *Centratherum anthelminticum*, saponin, acetylated, NMR spectroscopy, caulophyllogenin.

Introduction

Centratherum anthelminticum (L.) Kuntze (Synonym – *Vernonia anthelmintica* (L.) Willd.) belongs to the family Asteraceae (Compositae). In India, it is known as Kalajiri. It is black in colour and has a bitter taste. *C. anthelminticum* is an important medicinal plant and used in indigenous medicine or ayurvedic preparations in India¹. The seeds were reported to possess febrifugal, alterative, antihelminthic, antiphlegmatic, antifertility, antimicrobial, antifilarial, diuretic and digestive stimulant^{2,3}. Earlier phytochemical investigations revealed that the seeds of plant contain aliphatic fatty acids, bitter principle, novel steroids and glycosides⁴⁻⁸. In the present study, we report on the isolation and characterization of a two known β-sitosterol-3-*O*-glucopyranoside (**1**) and 3-*O*-[β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl]-hederagenin (**2**) and one new novel

triterpenoid glycoside 3-*O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-[α-L-arabinopyranosyl-(1→5)]-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-28-*O*-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→3)-β-D-glucopyranosyl]-16α,23-acetoxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (**3**) saponins. The two known saponins (**1** and **2**) are described for the first time from this species. Different extracts and compounds were also tested for antifilarial, antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities. Methanolic and aqueous extracts of seeds exhibited some pronounced pharmacological activities under study.

Results and discussion

The 70% EtOH extracts of the seeds of *Centratherum anthelminticum* were suspended in water and extracted successively with petroleum ether, EtOAc and *n*-BuOH. The EtOAc and *n*-BuOH portion was subjected to column

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

chromatography on RP-C18 and silica gel, affording known saponin (1) and (2) and one new triterpenoidal saponin (3). The known saponins (1) and (2) were identified as β -sitosterol-3-*O*-glucopyranoside and 3-*O*-[β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -L-arabinopyranosyl]-hederagenin on the basis of spectral data, especially 1D and 2D NMR and MS, and through comparison with the data available in the literature^{9,10}.

Compound (3) was obtained as a white amorphous powder and showed a positive reaction in the Liebermann-Burchard test and Molish's reactions indicating its triterpenoid glycosidic nature¹¹. In the IR spectrum there was no strong absorption band in the region 3500–3000 cm^{-1} instead a strong band at 1750 cm^{-1} and 1230 cm^{-1} clearly revealed the acetylation of the molecule. Bands in the region 1140–1060 cm^{-1} were attributed to C-O-C linkage in the molecule¹². The characteristic CH stretching and bending vibrations were obtained in the respective regions i.e. 2950, 1430 and 1360 cm^{-1} .

In the ^1H NMR spectrum the six singlets resonated at δ 0.74, 0.82, 0.90, 0.91, 0.98 and 1.06 were attributed to the six methyl groups of the triterpene moiety. The double doublet at δ 2.77 correspond to the H-18 proton. One of olefinic hydrogen in a trisubstituted double bond (δ 5.31, br s) and one double doublet at δ 3.45 attributed to the carbinolic hydrogen H-3 located at an axial position with a coupling constant value J 13.5 Hz (axial-axial interaction). The shielded position of H-3 (δ 3.45, Table 1) indicated that the OH-3 group is not acetylated i.e. this position is glycosylated. Further, the moderate deviation in the H-23 value of genin in the ^1H NMR (δ 3.92, 4.04) from the expected value is attributed to the stereoelectronic effect of the OH-3 sugar chain^{13–17}. The high field to low field correlation is observed between the most deshielded proton, a broad doublet at δ 5.82 and a proton of methylene at δ 1.46 and 2.12 by DQF-COSY. They correspond to α -OH at C-16 (-OCOCH₃) and H-15 (CH₂) and this can be rigorously demonstrated using ^{13}C arguments. The ^1H NMR revealed the presence of seven sugars in the molecule. Acetylation of the sugar was evident from the bunch of singlets observed in the region δ 1.94–2.2 of the spectrum.

In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of saponin, the signals attributed to the aglycone (genin) ranges from δ 10 to 50,

Table 1. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR data* of compound 3 (Aglycone)

Carbon No.	Type of carbon	^1H NMR, δ_{H} ppm (CDCl ₃ , 300 MHz)	^{13}C NMR, δ_{C} ppm (CDCl ₃ , 125 MHz)
1	CH ₂	1.52, 1.04 (m)	38.5
2	CH ₂	2.07, 1.38 (m)	25.2
3	CH	3.45 (m)	82.6
4	C	–	41.4
5	CH	1.05 (m)	47.6
6	CH ₂	1.36, 1.02 (m)	17.7
7	CH ₂	1.55, 1.12 (m)	32.4
8	C	–	39.0
9	CH	1.35 (m)	47.6
10	C	–	36.4
11	CH ₂	2.30, 1.80 (m)	22.8
12	CH	5.31 (br s)	122.8
13	C	–	142.8
14	C	–	41.5
15	CH ₂	1.46, 2.12 (m)	27.5
16	CH	5.82	78.2
17	C	–	46.4
18	CH	2.77 (dd)	40.0
19	CH ₂	1.65, 1.18 (m)	45.5
20	C	–	30.3
21	CH ₂	1.45, 1.10 (m)	33.5
22	CH ₂	2.10, 1.62 (m)	31.4
23	CH ₂	3.92, 4.04 (m)	65.2
24	CH ₃	0.82 (s)	12.6
25	CH ₃	0.98 (s)	15.8
26	CH ₃	0.74 (s)	16.8
27	CH ₃	1.06 (s)	25.2
28	C	–	175.2
29	CH ₃	0.91 (s)	32.7
30	CH ₃	0.90 (s)	23.3

*All assignments were based on DQF-COSY, TOCSY, HMQC and HMBC.

except those of C-23, C-3, C-12, C-13, C-16 and C-28. The double bond signals at δ 122.8 and 142.8 in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum indicated that the aglycone was an oleanane- Δ^{12} type. The peaks at δ 12.6, 15.8, 16.8, 23.3, 25.2 and 32.7 confirmed the presences of six methyl's. CH₂OH at C-23 was confirmed by signal at δ 65.2 while the signal at δ 175.01 was due to C-28 of the genin. In the spectrum, the signal for the C-16 was missing, which indicate substitution on this carbon. The presence of deshielded signal at δ 78.2 confirmed the position of acetylated α -OH at C-16 position.

After acetylation of the saponin, the sugar protons showed signals in the region δ 3.0–5.5 and their assignment is the basis of the sugar identification process. Increasing length of the sugar chains generated an entangled CHO area, whose analysis was performed by using 2D double quantum filtered correlated spectroscopy (DQF-COSY). Presence of seven sugars was evident from the six-anomeric proton signals observed at δ 4.35, 4.53, 4.69, 4.82, 5.13, 5.55 and 5.69. In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum signals at δ 89.7, 91.3, 97.2, 99.1, 100.3, 101.1 and 103.8 corresponded to the seven anomeric carbons. The chemical shift value indicated that five of them (δ 97.2, 99.1, 100.3, 101.1, 103.8) are glycosidic and a two (δ 91.3 and 89.7) is involved in an ester linkage. The ring protons of the monosaccharides residues were assigned from the TOCSY spectrum and the sequence protons in each residue was then deduced from ^1H - ^1H COSY experiment (Tables 2 and 3) and their respective ^{13}C values from HMQC spectra^{15–18} (Tables 2 and 3). A ^1H - ^{13}C

one bond chemical shift correlation experiment (HMQC) correlated all protons resonance with those of corresponding carbons. On the basis of ^1H chemical shift and $J_{\text{H,H}}$ coupling constant values¹⁸ (Tables 2 and 3), the ring size, configuration and conformation of six sugar residues were unambiguously determined. The absolute configuration of each sugar was inferred on the basis of its natural occurrence in saponosides.

The anomeric proton signal at δ 4.35 with a J value of 7.3 Hz allowed the sequential assignment of the signal from H-1 to H-6 including their multiplet patterns and coupling constants, which indicates the presence of a β -D-glucuronic acid. The signal at δ 5.69 was attributed to the anomeric proton of a pentopyranose, arabinose. The other three spin systems corresponding to two hexoses, β -D-glucose I, II (H-1 at δ 4.53 and 5.55) and one as pentose β -D-xylose (H-1 at δ 4.69) showed to be in the pyranoid form. The low field position of the H-1 signal (δ 5.55) for another glucose residue was attributed to a

Table 2. ^1H NMR chemical shift data* and ^{13}C NMR chemical shift data* (CDCl_3 , internal Me_4Si) for the sugar part at C-3 of compound (3)

Atom	β -D-Glc A		α -L-Ara		α -L-Rha I		β -D-Glc I	
	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C
H-1	4.35	103.8	5.69	89.7	4.82	99.1	4.53	100.3
H-2	3.96 ^a	73.5 ^a	4.88	70.1	5.19 ^a	68.4 ^a	3.81	76.8
H-3	4.95	72.6	5.46	75.4	5.03	70.7	5.15 ^a	73.8 ^a
H-4	5.24	68.2	5.09	73.8	3.58	72.2	4.85	70.5
H-5	3.84 ^a	73.2	4.20	78.9	3.84	66.2	3.58	72.6
H-6	3.56	169.9 ^a	4.67			17.1	4.28, 3.89	63.4
CH_3						1.15		

^aNon-anomeric protons and carbons at the position of interglycosidic linkages.

*Assignments may be interchanged within a column.

Table 3. ^1H NMR chemical shift data* and ^{13}C NMR chemical shift data* (CDCl_3 , internal Me_4Si) for the sugar part at C-28 of compound (3)

Atom	β -D-Glc A		α -L-Rha II		β -D-Xyl	
	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C	^1H	^{13}C
1	5.55	91.3	5.13	97.2	4.69	101.1
2	5.13	69.7	4.99	70.0	4.87	70.4
3	5.23 ^a	72.6 ^a	4.07	73.9	5.05	71.5
4	4.99	68.5	5.06	70.0	4.90	68.6
5	3.93	72.4	3.84	67.5	4.04	61.8
6-Ha	3.88	61.7		17.2	3.43	
6-Hb	3.56					
CH_3		1.18				

^aNon-anomeric protons and carbons at the position of interglycosidic linkages.

*Assignments may be interchanged within a column.

glycosidic linkage between the C-1 of this sugar unit and a carboxylic group (C-28) of the caulophyllogenin. The remaining two sugar residues (H-1 at δ 5.13 and 4.82) were concluded to be 6-deoxyhexopyranose, as also evident from two methyls observed at δ 1.15 and 1.18 confirmed them to be α -L-rhamnose I, II.

The signals between δ 60 and 105 contained resonances for all of the sugar carbons, except those of the methyl groups of the two rhamnose observed at δ 17.1 and 17.2. The deshielded position of C-3 (δ 82.6) indicated the glycosylation of the OH-3 group while the chemical shift of C-23 remains almost unchanged. Again the shielded position of the C-28 chemical shift (δ 175.01) is attributed to glycosylation of the carboxyl group of caulophyllogenin^{19–22}.

Partial structure comprising the oleanene skeleton was identified with the help of DQF-COSY experiments. Connectivity between different hydrogens and as well information on additional partial structures were obtained from the HMBC spectra which confirmed the presence of geminal dimethyl group (C₂₉-C₂₀-C₃₀), a geminal methyl-oxymethylene group (C₂₄-C₄-C₂₃), and rest three methyls at three quaternary carbons (C₁₀-C₂₅, C₈-C₂₆, C₁₄-C₂₇) through ³J_{C,H} and ²J_{C,H} correlations. In HMBC spectrum, the peak at δ 5.82 and 1.46 were correlated with δ 170 and 78.2 respectively, again confirming the acetylated α-OH at C-16 carbon.

The point of attachment of the oligosaccharidic chain and interglycosidic linkage was established by an HMBC experiment¹⁸. Thus, the correlation observed between C-3 of caulophyllogenin (δ 82.8) and H-1 of glucuronic acid (δ 4.35), between C-5 of glucuronic acid (δ 169.9) and H-1 of arabinose (δ 5.69), between C-2 of glucuronic acid (δ 73.5) and H-1 of rhamnose I (δ 4.82), between C-2 of rhamnose I (δ 68.4) and H-1 of glucose I (δ 4.53) unit confirmed the sequence linked at C-3 of the aglycone moiety.

The ¹³C NMR signal due to C-28 of the aglycone moiety at δ 175.01 together with signal of glucose II ester unit (δ 91.3) indicated esterification of the aglycone carboxyl group with this unit. The cross peak observed between H-1 of rhamnose II (δ 5.13) and C-3 of glucose II (δ 72.6) and C-3 of rhamnose II (δ 73.9) and H-1 of xylose (δ 4.69) unit from HMBC confirmed the sequence linked at C-28 of the aglycone moiety.

Therefore, the structure of the new triterpenoid glycoside **3** was characterized as 3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-[α-L-arabinopyranosyl-(1→5)]-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-28-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→3)-β-D-glucopyranosyl]-16α,23-acetoxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (**3**) on the basis of spectral data including evaluation of spin-spin coupling deduced by 1D and 2D NMR analysis together with the identification of the aglycone caulophyllogenin and sugars obtained (glucuronic acid, arabinose, xylose, rhamnose and glucose) from saponin hydrolysates. This is a novel compound and being reported first time by us from the *C. anthelminticum* seeds.

Pharmacological assay :

Screening of antimicrobial activity :

Agar diffusion technique was used for the screening of antibacterial and antifungal activities using paper disc

method²³. The results are being given in Table 4. The methanol extract showed very good activity against *Arthrobacter* while significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus*, while moderate activity showed against *Shigella flexneri* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. It also showed some activity against *Bacillus* species. The methanol extract showed very good activity against *Trichothecium roseum*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium solani*. While poor or no activity was observed against rest of the microorganism tested.

The compound **1** showed very good activity against *Arthrobacter* while significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus*. It showed moderate activity against *Shigella flexneri* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

The compounds **2** and **3** showed very good activity against *Arthrobacter* species and significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus*, while moderate activity against *Shigella flexneri* and *Salmonella typhimurium*. *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Escherichia coli* were found to be resistant against tested compounds. The compounds **2** and **3** showed very good activity against *Trichothecium roseum*, *Candida albicans* and moderate activity against *Fusarium solani* and *Penicillium notatum*.

Compound 1

Compound 2

Compound 3

Table 4. Screening of antimicrobial activity of compounds 1-3

Microorganisms	Methanol	Compound		
		1	2	3
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	10	10	11
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	6	-	8	-
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	7	-	8	-
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	10	8	-	6
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	14	11	7	-
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	19	13	11	14
<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	7	-	10	13
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	7	8	-
<i>Trichothecium roseum</i>	14	7	12	11
<i>Candida albicans</i>	11	7	12	15
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	13	7	-	7
<i>Penicillium notatum</i>	-	-	-	6

Disc diameter = 4 mm; - = No activity; + = 6.8-8.0 mm; ++ = 9.0-11.0 mm; +++ = 12-14 mm; ++++ = 16-20 mm.

Cytotoxicity :

To assess their mutagenic potential meristematic cells of *Allium cepa* L. root tips cells was used *in vivo*²⁴. For this aqueous and methanol extracts of *C. anthelminticum* seeds were prepared. A test solution of the seeds was prepared at two different concentrations 2.62 and 26.2 mg/mL. The extracts were utilized directly for experiments with *Allium cepa* L. root-tip cells. Onion bulbs (*Allium cepa* L.) were placed in flasks containing aerated water at room temperature until rooted, after which root sample were taken to act as time-zero (t_{zero}) controls. Some bulbs were then placed in the infusions prepared

above (controls were put in water) for 24 h, after which more roots were removed and the bulbs returned to water for 24 h to observe if there was recovery from any possible damage. The roots were fixed and stained using the Feulgen reaction and permanently mounted on slides. The slides were examined 'blind' (i.e. without knowing their treatments) using an optical microscope with a 40X objective. For each bulb 1000 cells were analyzed, i.e. a total of 6000 cells each for the control, treatment and recovery groups. Cells were examined for morphological and structural alterations, and the mitotic index (MI) was determined. Statistical analysis was done by the Chi-square test ($\alpha = 0.05$).

The results obtained with the extract of *C. anthelminticum* seeds, the total mean MI, the total number of analyzed cells, and the number of cells in each one of the different phases of the cell cycle (interphase, prophase, metaphase, anaphase and telophase), for each group of six onions, the controls and the treated plants were showed in Table 5. Only the treatment with both aqueous and methanol extracts of *C. anthelminticum* seeds at the higher concentration gave a result showing a statistically significant difference as compared to the control. The data obtained in these experiments, indicate that the extract of the *C. anthelminticum* seeds at the concentrations tested and used as described above, do not have mutagenic effects on metaphase chromosomes and do not affect cell division. In spite of the strong inhibition of cell division caused by the higher concentration of *C. anthelminticum*

Table 5. Treatment of *Allium cepa* L. root-tip cells with two different concentrations of *Centratherrum anthelminticum* seeds

Treatment (mg/mL)	Group	Cell total	MI (%) mean	Number of cells				
				I	P	M	A	T
Control	Co	6000	8.4	5497	236	104	95	68
	Tr	6000	7.8	5528	176	134	95	67
	Re	6000	7.8	5532	253	104	71	45
Aqueous (2.50)	Co	6000	9.0	5417	341	120	99	24
	Tr	6000	6.1	5635	181	92	68	25
	Re	6000	5.6	5665	140	98	63	33
Aqueous (25.0)	Co	6000	7.6	5539	272	84	60	45
	Tr	6000	1.5*	5937	24	28	7	4
	Re	6000	5.3	5681	176	70	55	23
Control	Co	6000	8.4	5497	236	104	95	68
	Tr	6000	7.8	5528	176	134	95	67
	Re	6000	7.8	5532	253	104	71	45
Methanol (2.50)	Co	6000	9.7	5417	330	115	91	47
	Tr	6000	8.0	5520	274	109	59	38
	Re	6000	6.9	5586	182	134	60	38
Methanol (25.0)	Co	6000	7.4	5555	273	93	42	37
	Tr	6000	1.4*	5918	38	25	15	4
	Re	6000	2.4	5858	82	38	12	10

I : Interphase; P : Prophase; M : Metaphase ; A : Anaphase and T : Telophase.

Co - Control - 0 h; Tr - Treatment - 24 h; and Re - Recovery - 24 h. *Statistically significant.

seeds extracts in the *Allium cepa* L. root meristem test system, this antiproliferative effect was rather cytostatic than cytotoxic, since there was recovery of cell division after replacement of the plant extract by water for 24 h. An antimitotic effect was only observed with the higher concentration of both *C. anthelminticum* seed extracts in *Allium cepa* L., and this effect was not irreversible, as cell division recovered within 24 h.

Materials and methods :

Optical rotations were measured with a Union PM-1 digital polarimeter. The Infra red spectra were recorded in KBr phase (range 4000–400 cm^{-1}) on Perkin-Elmer-377 Infracord spectrophotometer. The ESI mass spectra were recorded on Micromass Quattro II triple quadrupole mass spectra in CDCl_3 as solvent. NMR spectra were measured on a solution of the compounds in CDCl_3 at ambient temperature. The 1D and 2D NMR spectra (^1H - ^1H COSY, TOCSY, DQF-COSY, HMQC and HMBC) were performed using a varian DRX-300 MHz spectrometer and ^{13}C spectral analysis was performed at 75 MHz spectrometer. All chemical shifts (δ) are given in ppm and Me_4Si was used as an internal standard. The carbon

type (CH_3 , CH_2 , CH) was determined by DEPT experiments. Conventional pulse sequences were used for DQFCOSY, TOCSY, HMQC and HMBC. The sample was subjected to column chromatography using silica gel (E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) having a 70–230 mesh size. Thin layer chromatography was performed using pre-coated silica gel G-25-UV254 plates (E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) while its detection was observed by spraying with H_2SO_4 -vanillin or anisaldehyde solution followed by heating at 105 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min. For sugar analysis, paper chromatography was performed using Whatman filter paper No. 1 and was visualized by aniline hydrogen phthalate as the spraying agent.

Plant material :

The seeds of *Centratherrum anthelminticum* were collected from the local medicinal market of Ujjain city and were identified by the Professor D. M. Kumawat (Head), Institute of Environmental Management and Plant Sciences, Ujjain.

Extraction and isolation of the constituents :

The seeds (6.0 kg) were shade, dried, cleaned and

powdered coarsely. The powdered seeds were extracted with 70% EtOH serially for 72–92 h in soxhlet extractor. From the EtOH extract, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure by rotary film evaporator to yield a dark brownish residue (350 mg). The dried residue was suspended in water (1 L) and partitioned successively with petroleum ether, ethylacetate and *n*-butanol (each 3 × 1 L). The ethyl acetate soluble fraction (10 g) was fractionated on silica gel column, by eluting with different solvent mixtures in their increasing order of polarity. The *n*-hexane : EtOAc (1 : 9, v/v) elute showed two spot on TLC. Removal of solvent yielded two compounds in pure form designated as compounds (1) (60 mg) and (2) (55 mg). The *n*-BuOH-soluble fraction (41.5 g) was subjected to normal phase silica gel column chromatography. A portion of the elute CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O (26 : 14 : 3) was acetylated with acetic anhydride in the presence of pyridine (48 h; 25 °C; solvent, CHCl₃) and rechromatographed on a column of silica gel, using a discontinuous gradient from 3 : 1 benzene : EtOAc to 1 : 1 benzene : methanol. Fractions 40–50 (2500 ml) benzene : methanol (1 : 1) afforded the acetylated saponin (3). The following TLC solvent systems were used : for saponin **A**. CHCl₃ : MeOH : AcOH : H₂O (15 : 8 : 3 : 2); for saponin **B**. CHCl₃ : MeOH (9 : 1) for monosaccharides **C**. CHCl₃ : MeOH : H₂O (8 : 5 : 1).

β-Sitosterol-3-*O*-glucopyranoside (1) spectral data were in agreement with literature values⁹.

3-*O*-[β-D-Glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl]-hederagenin (2) spectral data in agreement with literature values^{10,11}.

3-*O*-[β-D-Glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-[α-L-arabinopyranosyl-(1→5)]-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-28-*O*-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→3)-β-D-glucopyranosyl]-16α,23-acetoxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (3) was obtained as pale white, shiny crystals (185 mg), [α]_D²⁵ (+25°) (c 1.6, CHCl₃).

Acid hydrolysis :

A solution of saponin (6 mg) in 80% methanol : benzene (5 mL) was refluxed for 5 h with 4 mL of 2 *M* HCl. The organic layer was evaporated under reduced pressure. Distilled water was added to reaction mixture and extracted with CHCl₃. The TLC analysis of the chloroform layer with **B** solvent system gives aglycone. The

aqueous layer was neutralized with aqueous NaOH 2% and concentrated under reduced pressure; the residue was compared with a standard mixture of the sugars with **C** solvent system using silica gel TLC. *R_f* for monosaccharides : 0.45 (Glc A), 0.34 (Glc), 0.29 (Ara), 0.20 (Rha), 0.25 (Xyl).

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